

Post-trial monitoring of a randomised controlled trial of intensive glycaemic control in type 2 diabetes extended from 10 years to 24 years (UKPDS 91).

Article summary:

A scientific article is about medicine, more precisely the field is: diabetology and endocrinology. The subject of the article is **monitoring patients after the completion of a randomized and controlled study of intensive glycemic control in type 2 diabetes**. A long-term prospective study was conducted in the UK and showed a large clinical benefit in patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes. 5102 patients were randomly assigned to intensive glycemic control with sulfonylurea or insulin or metformin therapy compared with conventional glycemia mainly diet. The study included a 20-year intervention period, followed by 10 years of patient follow-up to identify further treatment effects. The investigators wanted to see if these benefits were maintained, increased or decreased after the next period of monitoring. Of the 5102 patients in the period 1977-1991, 4209 were assigned to intensive glycaemic control with sulphonylurea, insulin or metformin (for overweight patients). The study also included a control group, people who used a more conventional approach, mainly following a healthy diet. After 20 years of intensive intervention and observation, 3277 patients survived. They then entered the 10-year follow-up phase. This phase ended in September 2007 and allowed the study authors to assess the effects of early glycaemic control after the main part of the study had ended. For an additional 14 years, the researchers continued to monitor the health of the study participants using data posted on the official NHS website. The information they collected was: ambulatory visits, number of patient deaths or hospitalizations. The analysis was conducted using statistical methods such as Kaplan-Meier analysis.

Results:

At the end of the 10-year post-study follow-up period, 1525 participants were enrolled in the project. Of these, 1489 (97.6%) could be linked to NHS administrative data. The mean age of participants at baseline was 50.2 years and 41.3% were women. At baseline, the mean age of participants was 70.9 years and by September 2021, the mean age of survivors was 79.9 years. Mortality data were collected from 130 participants from Northern Ireland, but lack of consent prevented analysis of other events. There were no significant differences in mean age or sex between participants at baseline.

Kaplan–Meier analyses showed that the separation of endpoints over time was proportional even after including NHS data. As of September 2021, 2809 of 4209 participants who were randomly assigned to intensive glycemic control (sulfonylurea, insulin, or metformin) or control. The median follow-up period ranged from 0 to 42 years. Follow-up increased by 21%, from 66,972 to 80,724 person-years. The median follow-up period was 17.3 years in the sulfonylurea or insulin group and 19.1 years in the metformin group. The glycemic control effects observed at post-baseline monitoring in the sulfonylurea or insulin groups were maintained for an additional 14 years.

The Kaplan-Meier curves remained separate, and the cumulative hazard ratios were constant. There was an overall reduction in the risk of death of 10%, myocardial infarction of 17%, and microvascular disease of 26%. The corresponding absolute risk reductions were 2.7%, 3.3%, and 3.5%. There were no significant reductions in the risk of stroke or

peripheral vascular disease. In the metformin group, the heredity effects were also maintained over the next 14 years. The risk reduction for death was 20% and for myocardial infarction 31%. The corresponding absolute risk reductions were 4.9% and 6.2%. There was no significant reduction in the risk of stroke, peripheral vascular disease, or microvascular disease with metformin. Direct comparison of hazard ratios between groups was also not possible because of subgroup limitations and differences in participant body weight.

List all the authors:

Amanda I Adler is a renowned diabetologist and epidemiologist, specializing in diabetes care, public health, and clinical trials. She has played a pivotal role in studies like the UK Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS), which has shaped diabetes management guidelines globally. Adler focuses on evidence-based approaches to chronic disease management and health policy. She is also active in public health advocacy and translational research, bridging clinical insights with policy to improve patient outcomes. She has an h-index of 47. Dr. Amanda I. Adler is associated with several prominent institutions. She is a consultant physician specializing in diabetes and cardiovascular epidemiology. Her primary affiliations include University of Oxford and National Institute for Health and Care Excellence.

Ruth L. Coleman is a researcher and head of the Statistics and Modelling Group at the Diabetes Trials Unit in the Radcliffe Department of Medicine at the University of Oxford. She has worked extensively on studies related to diabetes and cardiovascular diseases, particularly focusing on the impact of treatment strategies and disease progression. Coleman has authored and co-authored numerous significant publications. Some of her notable works include contributions to studies on intensive blood pressure treatment, the effects of medications like metformin and acarbose, and long-term diabetes management. She has an h-index of 21.

José Leal is a researcher and lecturer at the University of Oxford, specializing in health economics. He works with the Health Economics Research Centre (HERC), where his primary research focuses on the economic evaluations of chronic diseases, including cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and musculoskeletal diseases. His work also includes applying advanced methods like multi-parameter evidence synthesis and expert opinion to inform economic evaluations and decision-making in healthcare. José Leal works at the University of Oxford, specifically within the Health Economics Research Centre (HERC), which is part of the Radcliffe Department of Medicine. His h-index - 34.

William N. Whiteley is a Professor of Neurology and Epidemiology at the University of Edinburgh, where he works within the Centre for Clinical Brain Sciences and the Usher Institute of Population Health Sciences and Informatics. He is also a consultant neurologist in NHS Lothian. His research interests include the prevention of disability due to stroke and dementia, with a particular focus on the role of vascular risk factors in dementia. Whiteley is also involved in utilizing large datasets from electronic health records to improve the efficiency of clinical trials and cohort studies. He has an h-index of 54.

Philip Clarke is a prominent health economist with expertise in health economic evaluation, health inequalities, and the use of simulation models in healthcare. He is currently a professor at the Melbourne School of Population and Global Health, University of Melbourne,

and also serves as the Director of the Health Economics Research Centre at the University of Oxford. He has an h-index of 59.

Rury R. Holman is an internationally recognized clinical scientist and a key figure in diabetes research. He is the founder of the University of Oxford's Diabetes Trials Unit (DTU) and served as the first Professor of Diabetic Medicine at the university. He has led several landmark studies, including the UK Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS), which has shaped much of the current understanding of diabetes management. Holman is also involved in developing risk prediction models, such as the UKPDS Risk Engine and the UKPDS Outcomes Model, which are used by NICE to assess the impact of diabetes treatments. He has an h-index of 106.

Journal information:

The Lancet is a world-leading source of clinical, public health, and global health knowledge. The journal has an **Impact Factor of 98.4**, ranking first among 325 general and internal medicine journals globally (2023 *Journal Citation Reports*®, Clarivate 2024), and a **CiteScore of 148.1**, ranking first among 636 general medicine journals (Scopus).

The **Lancet** is a prestigious global medical journal publishing high-quality, peer-reviewed research across various healthcare fields. It is widely regarded as one of the top medical journals, influencing clinical practice, health policy, and medical research worldwide. Through its comprehensive range of journals, the Lancet Group connects researchers, clinicians, policymakers, and the general public, promoting the impact and dissemination of scientific findings.

The Lancet is known for its rigorous standards and commitment to advancing medical science, especially in areas such as public health, epidemiology, oncology, and global health. The journal has earned its reputation by publishing groundbreaking studies, often setting the agenda for medical research and policy worldwide.